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Enhancing Innovation and Development of Mongolian Dance

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ABSTRACT

Mongolian dance, as part of the traditional culture of the Mongolian ethnic minority in China, has a proven history of nearly a thousand years. Bowl dance, chopstick dance, Andai dance and Chama are the major folk-dance genres of the Mongolian dance, an artistical highlight in the cultural inheritance of the Chinese nation with strong ethnic characteristics. Amid the rapid growth of modern culture, Mongolian dance is confronted with certain challenges, and its innovation and development can be effectively enhanced by addressing these challenges.

INTRODUCTION

The Mongolian ethnic minority has been living in the vast prairie through the long course of history, which has generated a natural fit between the Mongolians and the prairie. Mongolians have also gradually developed broad minds, tough characters, and a unique ethnic culture of their own in such an environment. Mongolians are nomadic people, so their dance culture is closely associated with their nomadic lifestyle. After the founding of the People's Republic of China, Mongolian dance has regained attention and evolved from a traditional dance to a modern form of art. In the current context of globalization where various cultural exchanges are actively staged, Mongolian dance is facing both challenges and opportunities in its development. It is a priority to address the problems in the development of Mongolian dance, make vigorous innovations, and boost the innovation and development of the dance.

Innovation and Development of Mongolian Dance

The development of modern culture is based on traditional culture, and it also holds true for dances, a salient form of culture. However, against the backdrop of globalization featured by frequent cultural exchanges, various forms of art have gradually exerted their respective influences. The art of dance, by embracing modern arts and technologies, offers new opportunities for the development of Mongolian dance as new genres are derived from the traditional Mongolian dance after absorbing modern dance art. Mongolian dance needs to retain its ethnic characteristics in its innovation and development, but innovation of this form of art has been largely overlooked for the time being.

The innovation of Mongolian dance has started in the 1950s and the traditional Mongolian dance becomes more in line with modern aesthetics after being re-choreographed. The development of modern Mongolian dance has witnessed the emergence of many artists, such as Jia Zuozhuang, Siqintariha and Batu, as well as many excellent works. Mongolian dance has also provided some lessons for modern dances and folk dances. After innovation and development, Mongolian dance is exerting an increasing influence and is shining brightly in the palace of art.

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The innovation and development of Mongolian dance involve two dimensions: form and content. The artistic elements of Mongolian dance include music, costumes, props and stage, which are indispensable parts of the complete Mongolia dance and can strengthen its artistic and appreciation value. Besides, Mongolian dance gradually evolves towards diversification and can satisfy the needs of different viewers through the display of artistic elements. Continuous innovation is vitally important for Mongolian dance because it concerns the constant development of Mongolian dance. As a result, it is necessary to push Mongolian dance towards diversification amid cultural globalization (Buyinbatu, 2014).

Innovation is the basis of the continuous development of Mongolian dance. Mongolian dance needs to keep its traditional style while absorbing modern dance genres for innovation; otherwise, the Mongolian dance without its traditional style will change its nature. Inheritance and innovation are both crucial for the development of Mongolian dance, with the former being the foundation of the latter. Amid the wave of globalization that is featured by frequent cultural exchange, modern popular culture comes as a great shock to local cultures. How do we cope with the impact of foreign cultures and spread Mongolian dance to the world? To find answers, we need to strengthen the innovation of Mongolian dance and create modern innovations in concept, genre and music of the dance.

Problems in Innovation and Development of Mongolian Dance

Changes in the Cultural Foundation of Mongolian Dance

Mongolian dance boasts strong ethnic characteristics. Mongolians have been living in the vast prairie for generations and their long-standing nomadic culture contributes to the formation of this unique dance genre. The ethnic characteristics can be distinctly spotted from the postures and movements of Mongolian dance, which are deeply influenced by their lifestyle. For example, the back-and-forth shakes of a dancer's shoulders have to be fast and forceful, and the up-and-down movements have to be straight and unequivocal. This is closely associated with the lifestyle of Mongolians who have a lot of shoulder movements in lassoing horses. However, as time moves forward and modernization takes its course, the production mode and lifestyle of Mongolians have undergone some changes. For instance, the rising population has dramatically increased the demand for economic growth and resources, the fast-growing animal husbandry leads to a sharp increase in the consumption of grassland resources, and the gradual advent of grassland desertification is a result of the excessive consumption of grasslands by cattle and sheep. Mongolians that used to rely heavily on animal husbandry have now turned to agriculture and animal husbandry. Such changes have a certain impact on the genre of Mongolian dance. Moreover, the acceleration of urbanization and the impact of modern culture also leaves considerable impact on the development of Mongolian dance [2].

Ideological Constraints

Mongolian dance is a critical component of Mongolian culture and is of great significance in cultural inheritance. For example, Chama is a religious artistic activity in Buddhism used to carry forward the Buddhist doctrines, spread religious tenets and prevent evils. Chama's decisive position in Mongolian dance cannot be easily changed. People's ideas have gradually changed with social development, but it is not that easy to recognize and accept a foreign culture. Besides, compared with people living in coastal areas, Mongolians, who live in inland China, are less likely to embrace foreign culture or communicate with the outside world, thereby having a more conservative mindset. When it comes to innovation, they are usually confined to the dance genre of the ethnic minority and do not introduce new elements, which impedes innovation and development of Mongolian dance.

Impacts of Modern Culture

As modernization accelerates, people's living standard sees a gradual improvement, and there is a variety of literary and artistic works, which, coupled with the rise of Internet media, provide more diverse ways of entertainment. Currently, China's traditional literature and art are confronted with the impact of modern culture and are severely affected in terms of inheritance and development. Any literary or artistic activity is the result of human efforts. Yet, as modern and popular culture draws more attention from people amid the wave of modernization, traditional culture is largely overlooked.

The Mongolian dance is now facing challenges in two aspects in its development. First of all, the loss of people's attention to Mongolian dance results in a reduced number of platforms for its outward presentation. Besides, the dance is losing popularity among the mass due to the decrease in the number of professionals engaged in this dance. These two aspects greatly constrain the innovation and development of Mongolian dance.

Ways to Enhance the Innovation and Development of Mongolian dance

The key to enhancing the innovation and development of Mongolian dance is to look for innovation materials from its root, deeply experience Mongolians' life, carry forward the Mongolian traditional folk dance genre with ethnic characteristics, absorb the essence of modern culture for the innovation of Mongolian dance while maintaining its own characteristics, and gradually expand the influence of Mongolian dance.

Absorbing Advanced Modern Culture

Cultural development is a constant process. With the progress of the times, culture is endowed with different historical significances accordingly. The current society is developing towards diversification. What is needed in cultural development is to absorb the essence and discard the dregs and to integrate the characteristics of the times and develop a socialist culture with Chinese characteristics based on historical inheritance. As a traditional dance of the Mongolians', Mongolian dance demonstrates strong ethnic characteristics. Reform and innovation should be premised on maintaining its ethnic characteristics, and attention should be paid to the fact that traditional culture should not be forsaken while modern advanced culture is absorbed in the innovation initiatives. Judging from the status quo of Mongolian dance, its innovation is in a conservative state, so with a vision to boost innovation and development of Mongolian dance, it is necessary to stay open-minded, absorb essence of modern culture, and introduce new elements to the traditional forms of dances.

Carrying forward the Traditional Culture

The introduction foreign cultures to China since the Reform and Opening-up is a heavy blow to China's ethnic culture. With more attention drawn to the fresh and modern foreign cultures, the position of traditional culture is threatened. China, a country with a long history and many ethnic minorities, is characterized by inclusiveness since antiquity. When embracing foreign cultures, we must understand that cultural fusion should be built upon ethnic culture. Therefore, the key to carrying forward the traditional culture is to focus on localization. The innovation and development of Mongolian dance can be enhanced from two perspectives. First, we should get a clear view of the dance types and performance forms of Mongolian dance, refine and retain the dance genres with ethnic culture and aesthetic features, and lay the foundation for localization. Second, we should figure out the origin, development and historical significance of Mongolian dance, take them as the cultural foundation of Mongolian dance, enrich and polish such contents, expand its influence, attract more attention to Mongolian dance, and lay a good mass foundation for the innovation and development of Mongolian dance.

Drawing Lessons from Life

Art originates from life but goes beyond life. Modern Mongolian dance is based on the folk dance of the ethnic Mongolians, while folk dance is rooted in their lifestyle and customs. The innovation and development of Mongolian dance should be premised on deeply experiencing Mongolian's life, attaching importance to their folk dance, drawing lessons from life, inheriting their ethnic characteristics, and carrying forward Mongolian dance. Art gives expression to our life. If Mongolian dance needs to innovate, develop and represent Mongolians' life, there is no point in merely making innovations behind closed doors. Excellent dancers are not limited to the genre of Mongolian dance or the focus on the expression of emotions. Under the influence of modern dance culture, some Mongolian dance choreographers do not attach importance to the genre of Mongolian folk dance in their creation, and their innovative genre has failed to reflect the Mongolian styles and features. Consequently, it is a must to deeply experience the Mongolians' life, learn from their spiritual

temperament, combine one's feelings and elements of the times, and display the unique spiritual style of contemporary Mongolians through dance movements.

Strengthening the Publicity of Mongolian Dance

The modern world is in an information age when people communicate and disseminate information through the Internet. The influence of Mongolian dance can be publicized and expanded through the Internet. People are faced with multiple choices in the multicultural world, so the characteristics of Mongolian dance should be highlighted in its publicity to gain more attention. In addition, Mongolian dance contests can be held nationwide to engage more Mongolian dance enthusiasts and to further expand the influence of Mongolian dance. All these can enhance innovation and development of Mongolian dance (Mandi, 2014).

Conclusions

Several points deserve attention in the initiatives to enhance the innovation and development of Mongolian dance. First of all, we should identify the problems and the constraints in the innovation of Mongolian dance and be aware that innovation is necessary for its survival and long-term development in the megatrend of globalization. In addition, we should acquire a thorough understanding of the source and development trend of Mongolian dance. Modern Mongolian dance is rooted in the folk dance of the Mongolian ethnic minority, so its innovation should be focused on two points — to retain elements from folk dances, and to reflect the characteristics of Mongolian dance. The quality for Mongolian dance can be enhanced by making innovations on this basis. Last but not least, we should strengthen the influence of Mongolian dance and increase its popularity among the public. Modern Internet technology provides a feasible solution to publicize Mongolian dance with ethnic characteristics. Besides, Mongolian dance contests can be organized nationwide to engage more interested in this form of dance to boost its innovation and development. Against the backdrop of globalization, we should rely on the ethnic culture of Mongolians and increase the popularity of Mongolian dance among the public in our initiatives to innovate and improve this form of dancing art.

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